

Solvent Effect on the Kinetics of Reaction between Methyl Orange and Peroxydisulphate Ion in Presence of Bromide Ion – Separation into Transition State and Reactant Components

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Nuclear bromination was observed when methyl orange interacts with $S_2O_8^{2-}$ in presence of bromide ion. The reaction obeys zero order kinetics in the dye whereas first order kinetics in H^+ , $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and Br^- . Thus, the kinetics pertain to the rate-determining stage of peroxydisulphate – bromide reaction. The study in different acetic acid – water mixtures has shown that the rate increases with the increase in acetic acid content. The separation of the solvent effect into transition state and reactant components was accomplished from rate data and transfer free energies of $S_2O_8^{2-}$, Br^- and H^+ . The results indicate greater destabilisation of the reactants than transition state as acetic acid content is increased.

In strong mineral acid medium, *p*-dimethylaminoazobenzene and its derivatives do not react rapidly with peroxydisulphate, but in presence of bromide ion they are decolorised very easily. The strong absorption in 505–540 nm region is no more observed. It is necessary to examine whether the initial stage of the reaction involves nuclear substitution or oxidation. Hence a detailed investigation of this reaction has been taken up choosing methyl orange for this study. The results indicate that the kinetics pertain to nuclear bromination. An analysis of solvent effect of acetic acid on this reaction has enabled the dissection into effects on initial and transition states.

Experimental

All the chemicals employed were of analytical reagent grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout the investigation.

Kinetic study was made in aqueous sulphuric acid medium and the course of the reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of the unreacted methyl orange at 505 nm. At this wavelength, the dye has the maximum absorption and all the other materials concerned have negligible absorption. The kinetics were investigated at constant ionic strength maintained with sodium bisulphate. The kinetics of persulphate – bromide reaction were followed by measuring the optical density of bromine formed at 390 nm. Care was taken to see that the cells were tightly stoppered. The uv-visible spectra of the product and the reaction mixture at various time intervals, were scanned making use of a Shimadzu UV-260 spectrophotometer with microprocessor attachment.

Product analysis: Equivalent amounts of peroxydisulphate, methyl orange and bromide were mixed in 1M H_2SO_4 and after the completion of the reaction the product was extracted with ether and recrystallised from ethanol. The product gave a single spot on tlc plate with chloroform – methanol (1:1) as co-solvent. The uv-visible absorption spectra of the product showed the absence of 505 nm peak but a new peak was observed at 317 nm. The spectrum was identical to that of the monobromo derivative of methyl orange reported by Laitinen and Boyer¹. The spectrum of the reaction mixture was also scanned at different time intervals (Fig. 1). The spectrum shows that the intensity of peak at 317 nm increases and that at 505 nm decreases simultaneously with time. This indicates that the monobromoderivative is formed in the rate-determining stage. Since the kinetics of the reaction were investigated by measuring the optical density at 505 nm at different time intervals, the kinetics pertain to the formation of the monobromoderivative.

Results and Discussion

The reaction obeys zero order kinetics at least upto 80% of the reaction as shown by the linear plot observed between absorbance and time under the conditions $[S_2O_8^{2-}] \gg [Methyl\ orange]$. The pseudo-zero order rate constants (k_o), constant at different methyl orange concentrations under these isolation conditions, were calculated from the slopes of these plots. The values of k_o determined at different concentrations of $S_2O_8^{2-}$, the concentration of the other reactants being constant, were proportional to $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ (Table 1). Similarly, k_o was also directly proportional to $[Br^-]$ and $[H^+]$ (Tables 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. Spectra of the reaction mixture at different time intervals: (1) 3, (2) 10, (3) 20, (4) 30 and (5) 45 min, [Methyl orange] = 1.75×10^{-5} , $[Br^-] = 1 \times 10^{-2}$, $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ and $[H^+] = 5 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 0.2$ mol dm⁻³, temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Thus the empirical rate law can be expressed in the form,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Methyl orange}]}{dt} = k_s [S_2O_8^{2-}] [H^+] [Br^-]$$

Since zero order kinetics is observed in methyl orange, this will not participate in the rate-limiting step. Since the reaction obeys first order kinetics in $S_2O_8^{2-}$, H^+ and Br^- , all these ions must participate in the rate-limiting step. The following mechanism accounts for all the observed kinetics,

The formation of $BrSO_3^-$ in the rate-limiting step was also invoked by Uddin and Ghaziuddin² and Subhani³ in the oxidation of bromide ion by $S_2O_8^{2-}$.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ AND $[Br^-]$ ON THE RATE

[Methyl orange] = 1.17×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, $[H^+] = 1.00$ mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 3.20$ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Sl. no.	$[S_2O_8^{2-}] \times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	$[Br^-] \times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	$k_o \times 10^6$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
1.	4.00	1.00	1.11
2.	8.00	1.00	2.22
3.	10.0	1.00	2.78
4.	12.0	1.00	3.26
5.	16.0	1.00	4.40
6.	10.0	0.50	1.98
7.	10.0	0.75	2.08
8.	10.0	1.25	3.47
9.	10.0	1.50	4.10

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[H^+]$ ON THE RATE

[Methyl orange] = 1.17×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, $[Br^-] = 1.00 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 3.20$ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Sl. no.	$[H^+] \times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	$k_o \times 10^6$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
1.	2.00	0.56
2.	4.00	1.15
3.	5.00	1.45
4.	6.00	1.71
5.	8.00	2.27

The mechanism and rate-law require that the rate constant of decolorisation of the methyl orange should be equal to the rate constant of $S_2O_8^{2-}-Br^-$ reaction under identical experimental conditions. To test this, we determined the rate constant of $S_2O_8^{2-}-Br^-$ reaction under identical conditions. The rate constant, k observed ($2.82 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is in reasonable agreement with the specific rate constant of decolorisation of dye at 30° and $\mu=3.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Effect of solvent : Most of the organic solvents are oxidised by $S_2O_8^{2-}$. Hence acetic acid was chosen as the solvent which is resistant to oxidations by $S_2O_8^{2-}$. The reaction was found to be accelerated by the increase in the acetic acid content at constant $[H^+]$, which was adjusted by making use of expanded scale pH meter. Specific rate constant k_s was calculated from the equation,

$$k_s = k_o / [H^+][S_2O_8^{2-}][Br^-]$$

k_s was determined, at constant pH, at various compositions of the acetic acid - water mixtures.

Since zero order kinetics were observed with respect to the azo compound and first order kinetics in Br^- , $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and H^+ ions, transition state should contain only the latter ions. The solvent effect can be dissected into the reactant and transition state components and thus the change in the free energy of activation (when the solvent is changed from water to water - acetic acid mixtures) is equal to the difference in the free energy of transition state ($\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$) and the sum of the free energies of transfer (from water to this mixture) of H^+ , $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and Br^- ions. The transfer free energies of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ have been calculated from the solubility data. The solubility of $K_2S_2O_8$ in water and these solvent mixtures has been determined using the procedure described elsewhere⁸. The solubilities of the salt in water $S_{(w)}$ and the solvent mixtures $S_{(x)}$ are

related to the difference in the standard chemical potential $\delta\mu^\ominus$ (salt) by equation (1),

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\mu^\ominus(\text{salt}) &= \mu^\ominus(\text{salt}, x) - \mu^\ominus(\text{salt}, w) \\ &= nRT \ln (S_{(w)} \gamma_{\mp(w)} / S_{(x)} \gamma_{\mp(x)}) \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

where, $n=3$ in this case. The quantity $\delta_m\mu^\ominus(S_2O_8^{2-})$ was calculated assuming⁸ $\gamma_{\mp(w)} / \gamma_{\mp(x)} \approx 1$ using equation (1). The quantity $\delta_m\mu^\ominus(\text{salt})$ is related to the individual ions by equation (2),

$$\delta_m\mu^\ominus(K_2S_2O_8) = 2\delta_m\mu^\ominus(K^+) + \delta_m\mu^\ominus(S_2O_8^{2-}) \quad (2)$$

The Gibbs free energy of transfer for $S_2O_8^{2-}$ was calculated using the published⁴ values for K^+ . The values of $\delta_m\mu^\ominus(Br^-)$ and $\delta_m\mu^\ominus(H^+)$ were taken from the data reported⁴. From the rate constant in water and in the presence of the solvent mixtures, $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ was calculated using the equation (3),

$$k_s = \frac{kT}{h} e^{-\Delta G^\ddagger / RT} \quad (3)$$

$\delta_m\mu^\ominus^\ddagger$ for the activated complex was calculated from equation (4),

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger &= \delta_m\mu^\ominus^\ddagger - [\delta_m\mu^\ominus(Br^-) + \delta_m\mu^\ominus(H^+) \\ &\quad + \delta_m\mu^\ominus(S_2O_8^{2-})] \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

The results presented in Table 3 show that the free energy of activation becomes more negative as the acetic acid content is increased, which is consistent with the observed increase in rate under these conditions. This is in spite of the increase in the free energy of transfer of the transition state because the sum of free energies of transfer of the reactants (initial state) registers a greater increase as the acetic acid content is increased. As a consequence, the overall free energy of activation (which

TABLE 3—DISSECTION OF SOLVENT EFFECT ON THE $S_2O_8^{2-}, Br^-$ REACTION INTO INITIAL STATE AND TRANSITION STATE CONDITIONS FOR AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID

[Methyl orange] = $1.17 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 5.00 \times 10^{-2}$, $\mu = 0.200 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Br^-] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp = $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Acetic acid % (v/v)	Water	10	20	30	40	50	60
k_s ($\text{mol}^{-2} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$)	0.480	0.800	1.10	1.30	1.58	1.95	2.26
Solubility ($K_2S_2O_8$, mol dm^{-3})	0.210	0.182	0.100	0.080	0.056	0.043	0.030
$\delta_m\mu^\ominus(K_2S_2O_8)$, kJ mol^{-1} ^a		3.86	5.59	7.27	9.91	11.82	14.8
$\delta_m\mu^\ominus(K^+)$, kJ mol^{-1} ^a		0.084 ^c	0.790	1.55 ^c	2.34	3.05 ^c	3.85
$\delta_m\mu^\ominus(S_2O_8^{2-})$, kJ mol^{-1}		3.195	4.02	4.17	5.24	5.72	7.06
$\delta_m\mu^\ominus(Br^-)$, kJ mol^{-1} ^a		0.630 ^c	1.25	1.88 ^c	2.51	3.14 ^c	3.76
$\delta_m\mu^\ominus(H^+)$, kJ mol^{-1} ^a		0.210 ^c	1.21	2.59 ^c	3.97	5.43 ^c	6.69
$\delta_m\mu^\ominus_{i.s.}$ (kJ mol^{-1}) ^b		4.03	6.48	8.64	11.7	14.29	17.5
$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol^{-1})		-1.27	-2.07	-2.49	-2.99	-3.52	-3.89
$\delta_m\mu^\ddagger$ (kJ mol^{-1})		2.76	4.41	6.14	8.72	10.77	13.6

^aRef. 4. ^bi.s. = Initial state. ^cInterpolated from the data.

is difference between the transfer free energies of transition state and the reactants) decreases.

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